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SAYYID QOSIMIY VA TASAVVUF
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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada temuriylar saroyida xizmat Sayyid Qosimiyning mutasavviflar haqidagi hikoyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Unda muallifning shayx-valiylar obrazini yaratish borasidagi badiiy mahorati ma'lum bir hikoyatlar yordamida ochib berilgan. Xususan, Sayyid Qosimiy asarlari mazmunga shakl jihatidan qay darajada biriktirilganligi muallif asarlaridan olingan ijod namunalari misolida tahlil qilindi. Muallif hikoyatlar yozishda ko'p hollarda salafлари an'analariga tayanganligi ma'lum bo'ldi. Bu masala o'tmishda yashab o'tgan ulug' avliyolarning siymosi, ma'naviy olimini chuqurroq tasavvur qilishga yordam beradi. Masalaning hal qilinishi, birinchidan, tadqiq qilinayotgan asarlar mohiyatini yanada yaqqolroq ochishini ta'minlasa, ikkinchidan, uning o'ziga xos tomonlarini yoritishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: shayx, tasavvuf, hikoyat, poklik, Sharq, Islom, gado, faqirlik, fano, tarbiya.

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SAYYID QOSIMIY AND THE SUFIZIM**ANNOTATION**

This article analyzes the stories of Sayyid Qasimi, who served in the Timurid palace, about mystics. In it, the author's artistic skill in creating the image of sheikhs-wali is revealed with the help of certain stories. In particular, the extent to which Sayyid Qasimi's works are attached to the content in terms of form was analyzed on the example of creative examples taken from the author's works.

It turned out that the author relied on the traditions of his predecessors in many cases when writing stories. This issue helps to better imagine the figure of the great saints who lived in the past, the spiritual scientist. The solution of the problem, firstly, ensures that the nature of the researched works is revealed more clearly, and secondly, it serves to illuminate its specific aspects.

Keywords: sheikh, mystic, story, purity, East, Islam, gado, poverty, fano, upbringing.

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САЙИД КАСИМИ И СУФИЗМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируются рассказы Сайида Касими, служившего во дворце Тимуридов, о мистиках. В ней с помощью определенных сюжетов раскрывается художественное мастерство автора в создании образа шейхов-вали. В частности, на примере творческих примеров, взятых из произведений автора, проанализирована степень привязанности произведений Сайида Касими к содержанию с точки зрения формы. Оказалось, что автор во многих случаях опирался на традиции своих предшественников при написании рассказов. Этот выпуск помогает лучше представить себе фигуру великого святителя, жившего в прошлом, духовного ученого. Решение проблемы, во-первых, обеспечивает более четкое раскрытие сущности исследуемого произведения, во-вторых, служит освещению его конкретных сторон.

Ключевые слова: шейх, мистика, история, чистота, Восток, ислам, гадо, бедность, фано, воспитание.

In Eastern literature, storytelling is one of the genres that occupies a special place. It is known that Turkish storytelling has come a long way. If we look at the history of Uzbek classical literature, the stories are significant and they are important in the development of personal spirituality. The stories are mainly about the behavior of the people in the society, which serves to achieve purity in the inner world. Each story, of course, leads to certain ethical conclusions. Hence, in the East, high morals and decency, perfection and maturity, pure dreams, virtues and goodness were considered the main indicators. This, in turn, placed a responsibility on fiction as well. In particular, the epics in the spirit of exhortation, as well as the colorful stories in them, have a unique place.

For example, before Alisher Navoi, Uzbek written stories reached a high level in terms of subject and form. For example, the stories in Rabguzi's "Qisasi Rabguzi", Muhammad Ali as-Sarayi's "Nahju-l-farodis" (The open door to heaven), Sayfi Saroyi "Gulistani bit-turkiy" (Turkish flowerbet), Yusuf Amiri's "Dahnoma" (Ten letters), Haydar Khorezmi's "Gulshan ul-asror" (Flowerbet of secrets) are proof of this.

Another storyteller of this period is Sayyid Qasimi. The stories in his epics "Majma ul-Akhbar" (Message pack) and "Haqiqatnoma" (A letter of truth) are also distinguished by their variety of themes.

Mystical views have a wide place in the author's work. Therefore, the main characters of several stories in the works "Majma ul-Akhbar" and "Haqiqatnoma" are connected with the lives of people who are famous in the Islamic world. In particular, it is expedient to group Sayyid Qasimi's stories as "Stories about Sufis". They were told the following stories from "Majma al-Akhbar": "Shayx Shibliy va inidan uzoqlab ketgan lang chumoli" (Sheikh Shibli and the lame ant that ran away from his nest), "Shayx Junayd va qari it" (Sheikh Junayd and the old dog), "Zohid va fosiq" (Zahid and the wicked), "Pir va xasta shoh" (The old and the sick king), "Layli va Majnun", "Porado'z va uning kambag'al qo'shnisi" (Bribe-taker and his poor neighbor); The following stories can be included in the epic "Haqiqatnoma" (A letter of truth): "The Story of King Mardon", "The Story of Hasan Basri", "The Story of Ibrahim Adham", "The Story of Basri Hafi", "Ghaznavi alayhi-r-rahma", "The story of Imam Muhammad al-Ghazali and his soul", "The story of Sheikh, appearance and inner truth were not true", "The story of Hizr and his king and elder Pir Muqallad".

It is known that in mysticism there are specific maqams, and maqom means Arabic address, neighborhood, spiritual position, career, stop, place. [1:93] The names of this maqam are also referred to as sects. Y.E. Bertels: "The term sect can be replaced by the term leech ("journey"), which has almost the same meaning. The traveler who chose the journey was called a salih ("dervish"). Since

the image of the trip was included, of course, the image of the address (station) was also included. These addresses are represented by the term *maqam*, which is based on a verse from the Qur'an" [2:62] In particular, certain stages of these *maqams* are found in the works of Sayyid Qasimi. In particular, the second story of the epic "Majma' ul-akhbar" is called "Sheikh Shibli and the lame ant that moved away from his nest", which is about Sheikh Shibli. According to Alisher Navoi's *Nasayim ul-Muhabbat*, Junaid Baghdadi told Abu Bakr Shibli, "Every nation has a crown. The crown of this people is Shibli". It seems that this great sheikh was considered a man of great prestige. Nevertheless, Shibli himself is very humble, as can be seen in the following passage: "Shibli was asked, what is strange? He said, "He wants me to know the Almighty and to disobey him" [3: 197]

Let us now turn to the summary of Qasimi's story "Sheikh Shibli and the lame ant that moved away from his nest": "One day Shibli will get wheat from someone. While loading his horse, he sees a lame ant on one leg. Then she thinks that it is not a mercy to separate the ant from her husband, and she takes him to her place. It is a purely mystical story, guided by the idea of not hurting or hurting anything that God has created. In particular, this situation has a much wider place in the lives of mystics.

Let's focus on the following bytes of the story:

"...Aytdi: – Muruvvatdin emas mo'ri zor, Tushsa, yiroq manzilidin dilfigor. ...Qilma o'zingdin kishini xastadil, Bo'Imag'osen tangri qoshinda xijil. Har nechakim mo'r erur bas zaif, Quvvatu qahringa emasdur harif...Bandai dilxastag'a sen qilma, zo'r, Qolmag'asen nogah oldinda chu mo'r" (Shibli said: "It is not a mercy to lower an ant away from its nest". Do not make anyone else sick, for you will be ashamed in the sight of Allah. No matter how weak the ant is, Power and anger are not equal. Don't upset people.)[4:38]

Here, through the image of an ant, the author is also referring to human beings, because according to the Sufi worldview, no creature created by God should be persecuted. And man is the flower of this being. In this event, the mercy that is part of the *futuwwat* is glorified. N.Komilov writes about it: "So, *futuwwat* is a sect of courage. It is the science of mutual aid, kindness and compassion, devotion and devotion. The young man's words, deeds, intentions and thoughts were pure". [5:70] It turns out that showing mercy to a single ant is a great feat in itself. Indeed, the mercy bestowed on man is innumerable.

The story of the King of Mardon in the epic *Haqiqatnoma* also raises the issue of kingdom, poverty, courage, faith and love.

Hazrat Alisher Navoi writes in his radiant *ghazal* "Ango", which perfectly describes the relationship between the king and the *gado* of mystical philosophy:

"Shohlar darveshiyu darveshlar shohiki, bor, Shohlig' surat anga, darveshlik siyrat anga. To shahu darvesh bo'lg'ay aylagil, yo rab, ayon, Shohdin xidmat munga, darveshdin himmat anga". (He is the dervish of kings. No, don't say that. He is the king of dervishes. The kingdom is his appearance. Darwishism is in his inner world.)[6:29]

Just as there are criteria of perfection for each period, so in classical literature one of the distinctive features of the fifteenth century is whether this dervish or king is not defined by that image, but by the inner world. We see in the following verse about Hazrat Ali that certain aspects of this concept, which Navoi envisioned, are also reflected in the story of "Shahi Mardon": "Mayi gulgun ichu qil porsoyi, Gadolik kisvatinda podshoyi"(Drink red may and be divine. Be a king in poor clothes). [4: 138]

Sayyid Qasimi also lived in the palace. His ideal, therefore, was a *gado* in the form of a king whose inner world was accustomed to poverty. He promotes the idea that the king should have the quality of poverty. As the king becomes arrogant, oppression and injustice begin in the land. The fact that the writer wanted the Timurid sultans and rulers to be formed as such a brave, noble, poor man, of course, is reflected, at least in part, in his story. The guy in love in the story is ready for anything for love. Hazrat Ali also showed mercy to the young man in love. Because Hazrat Ali is also a person who understands love and romance well.

The kindness of Alisher Navoi in "Nazm ul-Jawahir" (Poetic gems) can be seen in the following *rubai* of Hazrat Ali, who linked his words to his words:

“Har kimsaki, din ichinda quvvat yo‘q anga, Jazm aylaki, oni futuvvat yo‘q anga. Din ahli bila rasmi uxuvvat yo‘q anga, Ul kimsada yo‘q dinki muruvvat yo‘q anga”. (Everyone, there is no power in religion, there is no power in religion, there is no power in religion. The people of religion know that there is no official mercy, and no one has religious mercy) [7:83]

The story of Ibrahim Adham is one of the most famous stories, and we find stories about him in almost every work. For example, in the story of Ibrahim Adham and Robiya Adviya in Navoi’s Hayrat ul-abror, we see certain qualities about both individuals, including sincerity and love. Similarly, in the story “Ibrahim Adham” in Sayyid Qasimi’s “Haqiqatnoma”, this man’s qualities of humility, courage, arrogance, and self-control are evident.

In the story of “Junaid Baghdadi” in the epic “Majma’ al-Akhbar”, the quality of vigilance is at the forefront, because his teachings are erroneous. This sect emerged on the basis of the Taifurian series. If the Taifuriyyah propagated sukr-drunkenness until it reached the place of death with the remembrance of Allah, then the teachings of Junaydiya supported its opposite vigilance. According to the Junaids, drunkenness brings danger and calamity to man and makes him anxious. Intoxication, which is a sign of death, is not necessary. It is therefore necessary to understand Allah with vigilance; negligence, sleep, and drunkenness have never been of any use, and even in prayer its futility has been known. But vigilance leads to happiness”. [8: 122]

The story of “Zahid and the Wicked” in “Majma al-Ahbar” describes the virtues of patience and wisdom. This story is contained in chapter 16 of the work, and the summary is as follows: In the city of Kufa, a drunken drunkard was caught by the neck of a pious hermit. The ascetic was extremely patient, so he would never be upset by the work of a drunken man. At that moment, someone came and said to the hermit, “Why don’t you hit him with your hand, because you are alive?” Zahid, back away from that. That is to say, the wicked do not know what a fool he is, but I know. He says that if I hit him in this position and take him by the collar, I will become a worse person. He is ashamed to say this and goes home. Patience and wisdom are glorified in this story. Qasimi writes about this: “Mardi karam was very patient, he was not sick and upset” [Because patience has a special place in mystical positions. “Patience is the first step in the path of risk” is mentioned in the sources” [9: 853]. A hermit is a person who has entered the path of asceticism and left the world. Zahid managed to make him repent by showing his two qualities to the wicked one who grabbed him by the collar, the first being patience and the second being wisdom. The reason: when Zahid also fought him, his reputation would be lost. So, in the story, such qualities as not speaking inappropriately, refraining from lust, anger, self-awareness, and being polite in everything you do are also glorified.

In general, Sayyid Qasimi’s stories, which reflect mystical figures, reveal only certain aspects of the sheikhs and governors, as well as one aspect of their manners. There are many such stories in the East. Therefore, although they are similar in form to each other, they are not close in content.

Sayyid Qasimi’s work made a significant contribution to the development of pre-Navoi Turkish literature. His epic writing skills, especially noteworthy, show that the predominance of mystical ideas in his epics continued the work of his predecessors and gave a new form to these stories.

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